

AI-Driven Early Detection of Sepsis and Utilization of Unstructured Healthcare Data for Improved Diagnosis

¹Mukesh Kumar Saini, ²Brett Fritze

¹Researcher and Solution Architect, ²Product and Technology Consultant
¹Wipro Limited, ²HCA Healthcare

ABSTRACT: Sepsis remains a leading cause of mortality in hospital settings, with its early prediction and diagnosis being critical to improving patient outcomes. The challenge lies in the fact that sepsis symptoms often mimic those of less severe conditions, complicating early detection. To address this issue, we present the SERA algorithm, an advanced artificial intelligence (AI) tool designed to enhance the early prediction and diagnosis of sepsis. The SERA algorithm leverages both structured data, such as vital signs and laboratory results, and unstructured clinical notes, including physician narratives and patient histories.

Our study evaluates the performance of the SERA algorithm using a dataset of independent clinical notes and demonstrates its capability to predict sepsis with high accuracy up to 12 hours before its clinical onset. The algorithm achieves an area under the curve (AUC) of 0.94, with sensitivity and specificity rates of 0.87 each, indicating strong predictive performance.

In a comparative analysis with traditional physician predictions, the SERA algorithm shows a potential improvement in early sepsis detection by up to 32%, highlighting its enhanced ability to identify patients at risk earlier. Additionally, it reduces the incidence of false positives by up to 17%, thereby improving diagnostic precision. The incorporation of unstructured clinical notes into the algorithm significantly boosts its accuracy over models relying solely on structured clinical measures. This improvement is particularly notable in the 12 to 48-hour window preceding sepsis onset, underscoring the value of integrating diverse data sources for more effective early warning systems.

Our findings suggest that the SERA algorithm represents a promising advancement in sepsis prediction and diagnosis, offering the potential to reduce mortality rates and improve patient outcomes through timely intervention.

Keywords - Sepsis, Artificial Intelligence (AI), SERA Algorithm, Structured Data, Unstructured Data, Clinical Measures, Mortality Reduction, Healthcare Analytics, Machine Learning, Risk Assessment, Patient Outcomes.

I. INTRODUCTION

Sepsis is a major cause of death in hospitals across the United States [1], responsible for about half of all hospital fatalities [2]. Early detection is essential for reducing mortality, as managing sepsis is highly time-sensitive [3]. International medical guidelines [4] recommend starting fluid resuscitation within the first 3 hours to address tissue hypoperfusion [4] caused by sepsis and initiating intravenous antimicrobial treatment within 1 hour of sepsis [4-6] onset. Delays in administering [5,6] antimicrobials significantly increase mortality rates. Standardized management approaches [4] can make early sepsis detection challenging, and operational issues in healthcare, such as delays in communication among clinicians, nurses, and pharmacists, can further exacerbate the problem. Therefore, early prediction of sepsis before its onset provides clinicians with valuable lead time to plan and implement treatment strategies effectively.

Current methods for diagnosing and predicting sepsis primarily utilize structured data from electronic medical records (EMRs) [7-9]. However, about 80% of clinical data in EMRs are unstructured—such as free-form text (e.g., clinical notes) and images (e.g., radiological scans). This unstructured data often contains rich, detailed clinical information that structured data fields might not capture. Physicians rely on unstructured data for documenting detailed clinical notes and reviewing critical information from other clinicians, which helps them understand a patient's condition and treatment effects better. Thus, unstructured EMR data present a valuable resource for developing advanced artificial intelligence (AI) tools, particularly for conditions like sepsis, where early

symptoms can be ambiguous and difficult to identify. Recent research has begun to leverage text-mining of clinical notes to enhance the accuracy of early sepsis prediction [10-12].

In the field of clinical notes mining, researchers have employed natural language processing (NLP) to identify and extract medical events, medication details, and clinical workflows from unstructured text data in electronic medical records (EMRs). Most NLP applications have focused on extracting specific concepts from clinical notes. Our study builds on these existing text-mining algorithms for sepsis prediction by enhancing their accuracy and extending the early warning period to up to 48 hours [13-16]].

Diagnosing sepsis can be challenging due to the diverse sources of infection and the wide range of patient responses. Previous research has utilized text mining to improve sepsis prediction by extracting common words from clinical notes to enhance model accuracy [11,12]. In contrast, our study advances this approach by demonstrating that modeling common topics, rather than individual words, can achieve greater predictive accuracy and extend the prediction window up to 48 hours before sepsis onset. We advocate for using topics because they provide more stable and generalizable insights compared to individual words, which can vary significantly due to different physicians' writing styles. This approach helps overcome the limitations posed by idiosyncratic terminology and improves overall prediction reliability [17,18].

Our study introduces a topic-based NLP-enabled AI algorithm that integrates NLP analysis of clinical notes with structured EMR data to better predict sepsis risk. The algorithm extracts and summarizes information from clinical notes and combines it with structured data to classify current sepsis status and predict future risk at 4, 6, 12, 24, and 48 hours. This model is effective even with a low sepsis prevalence of 6%, matching historical hospital data. We found that incorporating clinical notes significantly improves prediction accuracy, especially for forecasts 12-48 hours ahead of sepsis onset, surpassing the accuracy of physician predictions. Given that delays in sepsis management can increase mortality rates, our algorithm's ability to expedite diagnosis and early detection could significantly reduce hospital mortality rates [19,20].

II. RESULT

Data and data processing

This study focuses on patients admitted to a HCA's hospital, with details on sampling provided in the "Methods" section. We define sepsis using ICD-10 codes for sepsis, severe sepsis, or septic shock, combined with ICU admission records. According to hospital protocols, patients diagnosed with sepsis are transferred to the ICU; thus, those with one or more of these ICD-10 codes and admitted to the ICU are classified into the sepsis case cohort. Patients who do not meet these criteria are classified into the non-sepsis control cohort. Our dataset includes 240 sepsis patients in the training and validation sample and 87 sepsis patients in the test sample. For our study, sepsis onset is defined as the time of ICU ward admission, in line with hospital practice [19-,21,23].

In our case-control sample, sepsis prevalence is 6.15%, which aligns with the estimated sepsis prevalence of about 6% in hospitals. To address the data imbalance, we applied the Synthetic Minority Over-sampling Technique (SMOTE) to balance the dataset at a 1:1 ratio for sepsis cases and non-sepsis controls at the clinical note level. Previous research suggests that oversampling, rather than under sampling, enhances model accuracy, and SMOTE has been successfully used in machine learning classifiers for conditions like oral cancer detection and cell identification, where positive case prevalence is low. Additionally, for comparative analysis, we also developed and tested models without oversampling to evaluate performance in a typical clinical setting where sepsis prevalence is relatively low [22,24,25].

Sepsis early risk assessment (SERA) algorithm

Figure 1 illustrates the development process for the SERA algorithm. The algorithm is designed to analyze each patient consultation instance, leveraging both clinical notes and structured data to assess sepsis risk. This approach aligns with the typical clinical workflow, where clinicians evaluate and diagnose patients during consultations.

The SERA algorithm is composed of two interconnected components: a diagnosis algorithm and an early prediction algorithm. The diagnosis algorithm assesses whether the patient has sepsis at the time of consultation. If sepsis is not identified, the early prediction algorithm then estimates the patient's risk of developing sepsis in the next 4, 6, 12, 24, and 48 hours. For the diagnosis algorithm, we integrated clinical notes from the EMR system with the most recent structured variables listed in Table 1 for each patient consultation. This combined data is used to determine whether the patient has sepsis at the time of consultation.

The flow diagram outlines the development of the SERA Algorithm, incorporating both structured data (vital signs, investigations, and treatments) and unstructured data (clinical notes) to diagnose and predict sepsis.

Table 1 List of structural variables used in the predictive algorithm.

Category	Predictors
Patient information	Age, gender
Vital signs	Blood pressure, heart rate, temperature, oxygen saturation, respiratory rate
Investigations	Total white cell, culture results ^a , lactate, high-sensitivity C-reactive protein, procalcitonin, arterial blood gas
Treatment	Use of vasopressor, use of antibiotics

^aThe cultures include: the culture of urine, blood culture (anaerobic/aerobic), general culture, wound culture, stool culture, molecular, fluid culture, respiratory culture, cerebrospinal fluid culture, fungus smear, tissue culture, fluid culture (bactec bottle), fluid culture (aerobic), ear culture, genital culture, sterility testing, tip culture, wound culture (aerobic), appearance, stain results, or any real-time polymerase chain reaction. Cultures are typically used to confirm test presence of carbapenem-resistant enterobacteriaceae, methicillin-resistant staphylococcus aureus, clostridium difficile antigen, clostridium difficile toxin, clostridium difficile influenza, influenza B (real-time polymerase chain reaction), influenzae virus, strep pneumoniae antigen, carbapenem-resistant enterobacteriaceae screening, hepatitis viral load, cytomegalovirus, methicillin-resistant staphylococcus aureus screening, legionella antigen, sarcoptes scabiei, herpes simplex virus.

In contrast, the early prediction algorithm uses a similar data structure but excludes consultations from patients who have already been confirmed to have sepsis and are transferred to the ICU. This exclusion is crucial to avoid biasing the algorithm's predictive power, as consultations with confirmed sepsis are likely to display characteristics strongly associated with the condition.

Processing of Clinical Notes and Machine Learning

Before incorporating unstructured clinical notes into the algorithm, we processed these notes using natural language processing (NLP), specifically employing the Latent Dirichlet Allocation (LDA) topic modeling technique. This approach allowed us to extract and numerically weight the major topics within the progress notes. We identified 100 common topics, which were categorized into one of seven groups: (1) clinical status, (2) communication, (3) laboratory tests, (4) non-clinical status, (5) social relationships, (6) symptoms, and (7) treatment. These numerical topic loadings were then combined with the structured data variables listed in Table 1 to serve as predictors in both the diagnosis and early prediction algorithms.

In the diagnosis algorithm, we utilized a voting ensemble machine learning method to classify whether a patient has sepsis at the time of consultation. For comparison, we also tested the performance of two alternative classifiers: dagging and gradient boosted trees (GBT).

For consultations where the patient is not classified as having sepsis, the early prediction algorithm evaluates the risk of developing sepsis in the next 4, 6, 12, 24, and 48 hours. This prediction is based on the voting ensemble machine learning method, which uses the numerical topic loadings and structured data as predictors. The dependent variables for the early prediction algorithm are the probabilities of the patient developing sepsis within each of these time frames.

The trained and validated models are then evaluated using an independent, hold-out test sample. Detailed methodological information about the text-mining process, diagnosis algorithm, and early prediction algorithm can be found in the "Methods" section.

We present the test results for the SERA algorithm under two conditions: oversampled data using the Synthetic Minority Over-sampling Technique (SMOTE) and non-oversampled data. The results for the SMOTE models reflect typical outcomes in machine learning predictive models where the prevalence of sepsis cases is balanced with non-sepsis cases (see Table 2). In contrast, the non-SMOTE models demonstrate performance in standard clinical settings where sepsis prevalence is relatively low (see Table 3). For conciseness, we will focus on discussing the results for the SMOTE models, as they align with findings from prior studies [22,24,25].

Table 2 Statistics of diagnosis and early prediction algorithm (SMOTE).

Diagnosis algorithm								
Outcome predict if the patient has sepsis	Voting						Dagging	GBT
At the present time	AUC	Sensitivity	Specificity	PPV	NPV		AUC	AUC
	0.94	0.89	0.87	0.85	0.90		0.92	0.94
Early prediction algorithm								
Outcome predict if patient will have sepsis	Voting						Dagging	GBT
48 h later	AUC	Sensitivity	Specificity	PPV	NPV		AUC	AUC
24 h later	0.87	0.78	0.77	0.77	0.78		0.83	0.83
12 h later	0.90	0.81	0.80	0.80	0.80		0.86	0.86
6 h later	0.94	0.87	0.87	0.87	0.87		0.92	0.92
4 h later	0.92	0.88	0.81	0.82	0.87		0.90	0.93
	0.92	0.86	0.80	0.81	0.86		0.85	0.92

SMOTE applied to clinical notes to achieve a balanced sample of sepsis and non-sepsis case entries. SERA algorithm uses the voting algorithm; dagging and GBT algorithms are presented for comparative purposes.

Table 3 Statistics of diagnosis and early prediction algorithm (in low prevalence condition without SMOTE).

Diagnosis algorithm								
Outcome predict if the patient has sepsis	Voting						Dagging	GBT
At the present time	Prevalence	AUC	Sensitivity	Specificity	PPV	NPV	AUC	AUC
	0.177	0.94	0.89	0.87	0.59	0.97	0.92	0.94
Early prediction algorithm								
Outcome predict if patient will have sepsis	Voting						Dagging	GBT
48 h later	Prevalence	AUC	Sensitivity	Specificity	PPV	NPV	AUC	AUC
24 h later	0.012	0.87	0.76	0.76	0.04	0.99	0.82	0.85
12 h later	0.010	0.90	0.81	0.79	0.04	0.99	0.88	0.89
6 h later	0.008	0.94	0.88	0.82	0.04	0.99	0.92	0.93
4 h later	0.002	0.92	0.88	0.83	0.01	0.99	0.90	0.93
	0.001	0.92	0.89	0.87	0.01	0.99	0.92	0.94

No oversampled applied. Prevalence is computed at the clinical note level. For the same number of sepsis cases, the clinical note occurrences are different for a different time window. SERA algorithm uses the voting algorithm; dagging, and GBT algorithms are presented for comparative purposes.

For the diagnosis algorithm, the test sample yielded impressive results with an AUC of 0.94, sensitivity of 0.89, specificity of 0.85, and a positive predictive value (PPV) of 0.85. This AUC is notably higher than those reported in previous studies, which range from 0.64 to 0.92 [7,9,11,12,26-31].

The SERA algorithm also excels in predicting sepsis risk before physicians diagnose it. For predictions made 48 hours before sepsis onset, the algorithm achieved an AUC of 0.87. This AUC improves to 0.90 when predicting 24 hours ahead and reaches 0.94 at a 12-hour lead time. These results are superior in AUC, sensitivity, specificity, and PPV compared to prior research. For instance, our 12-hour lead time prediction outperforms previous models in these metrics. The 24-hour lead time prediction also demonstrates a high AUC of 0.90, with sensitivity, specificity, and PPV values of at least 0.80 [8,11,12,32].

This extended early prediction capability is critical for improving clinical outcomes, as delays in antimicrobial administration can decrease patient survival by 7.6% for each hour of delay. The additional 24 hours provided by our algorithm offers clinicians valuable time to prepare and implement timely interventions for sepsis management.

SERA algorithm vs. human prediction

We compared the performance of the SERA algorithm with established predictive scoring systems commonly used in clinical practice, such as the Systemic Inflammatory Response Syndrome (SIRS), Sequential Organ Failure Assessment (SOFA), quickSOFA (qSOFA), and Modified Early Warning System (MEWS). These systems are employed to diagnose sepsis or predict mortality due to infection.

According to a meta-analysis study, the typical performance metrics for these scoring systems at 4 hours before the onset of sepsis are as follows: the Area Under the Curve (AUC) ranges from 0.50 to 0.78, the True Positive Rate (TPR, or sensitivity) ranges from 0.56 to 0.80, and the False Positive Rate (FPR, or 1—specificity) ranges from 0.16 to 0.50.

We plotted the ROC curves of the SERA algorithm against these established scoring systems, as shown in Figure 2a, to visually compare the predictive performance. This comparison highlights how the SERA algorithm's early prediction capabilities stack up against traditional methods in terms of sensitivity and specificity for sepsis prediction.

Additionally, we assessed the performance of hospital physicians in diagnosing sepsis by analyzing the timing of their diagnostic actions. According to medical guidelines, physicians should initiate lactate normalization and obtain appropriate microbiologic cultures before starting antimicrobial therapy if sepsis is suspected. Consequently, in our evaluation, we defined the moment a physician orders both culture and lactate tests as the point at which sepsis suspicion is raised [8].

We then determined the prediction time window as the interval between when these orders are placed and when sepsis actually develops. Using this approach, we calculated the True Positive Rate (TPR) and False Positive Rate (FPR) for physician diagnoses at five different time points: 48, 24, 12, 6, and 4 hours before the onset of sepsis.

Figure 2a illustrates that, at 4 hours before sepsis onset, the SERA algorithm outperforms hospital physicians in predicting sepsis within the test sample. Moreover, the SERA algorithm exceeds the typically reported accuracy rates of traditional human-based scoring systems such as qSOFA, MEWS, SIRS, and SOFA, as indicated by prior studies. This demonstrates the superior predictive capability of the SERA algorithm compared to both conventional scoring methods and physician-based predictions.

Figure 2b displays the ROC curves for the early prediction algorithm at various time points: 48, 24, 12, 6, and 4 hours before sepsis onset. The ROC curves demonstrate improvement from 48 hours to 12 hours before sepsis and remain stable beyond the 12-hour mark. At all evaluated time periods, the SERA algorithm consistently outperforms hospital physicians' predictions.

For a conservative comparison, we evaluated the SERA algorithm's performance at 48, 24, 12, 6, and 4 hours before sepsis against the accuracy of traditional scoring systems—MEWS, qSOFA, SIRS, and SOFA—at the 4-hour mark as reported in the literature. The SERA algorithm showed superior performance across all time periods, surpassing the prediction accuracy of these scoring systems even when assessed at the 4-hour threshold.

To assess the practical utility of the early prediction algorithm, we computed the True Positive Rate (TPR) and False Positive Rate (FPR) for the SERA algorithm at 48, 24, 12, 6, and 4 hours before sepsis onset (Fig. 3). The algorithm achieved a TPR of 0.78 at 48 hours before sepsis, which improves to at least 0.86 for time periods less than 12 hours before onset. In contrast, hospital

physicians detected only 0.53 of eventual sepsis cases at 48 hours, with a marginal increase to 0.58 at the 6-hour mark and a notable rise to 0.65 at 4 hours. Overall, the SERA algorithm demonstrated a higher TPR by 0.21 to 0.32 compared to hospital physicians at all time points, indicating a potential 21-32% improvement in early sepsis detection. This suggests that the SERA algorithm could significantly enhance early sepsis detection compared to traditional physician assessments alone.

The False Positive Rate (FPR) of the SERA algorithm ranges from 0.23 at 48 hours before sepsis to 0.13 at 12 hours before onset (Fig. 3b). In comparison, the FPR for hospital physicians' predictions is notably higher, ranging from 0.34 at 48 hours to 0.27 at 4 hours before sepsis onset. This indicates that the SERA algorithm could reduce false positives by 0.07 to 0.17, thereby improving diagnostic precision.

Figure 3 highlights that the TPR and FPR of hospital physicians peak only at the 4-hour mark. This suggests that physicians typically have a much shorter lead time for medical intervention. In contrast, the SERA algorithm offers significantly earlier predictions, up to 48 hours before sepsis onset. This extended lead time provides physicians with earlier warnings of potential

sepsis, enabling more proactive and potentially more effective interventions.

Benefits of unstructured clinical text in early sepsis prediction

To quantify the added predictive value of unstructured clinical notes in the SERA algorithm, we conducted an analysis comparing the performance of the algorithm using only structured variables (as listed in Table 1) with the performance of the algorithm that incorporates both structured and unstructured clinical notes.

We assessed the algorithm's performance based on its ability to diagnose and predict sepsis with structured data alone, and then compared it to the performance of the enhanced algorithm that also includes information extracted from unstructured clinical notes. The results of this comparison are illustrated in Figure 4.

This analysis allows us to measure how much the inclusion of unstructured clinical notes improves the predictive accuracy of the SERA algorithm, offering insights into the value added by integrating diverse data sources.

Our analysis revealed that incorporating unstructured clinical text into the SERA algorithm enhanced its performance, but the extent of improvement varied depending on the time frame:

Short-Term Predictions (up to 6 hours before sepsis onset): The addition of clinical text yielded only marginal improvements in the algorithm's performance for diagnosing and predicting sepsis. This suggests that in the short term, the structured variables—such as blood pressure readings—already capture most of the relevant symptoms of sepsis.

Longer-Term Predictions (12 to 48 hours before sepsis onset): The integration of unstructured clinical text provided substantial benefits. Specifically, the use of clinical text improved:

- **AUC:** By 0.10 to 0.15
- **Sensitivity:** By 0.07 to 0.13
- **Specificity:** By 0.08 to 0.14

These improvements highlight that for early predictions within the 12 to 48-hour window before sepsis onset, unstructured clinical notes offer significant added value. During this period, patients have not yet exhibited the more overt symptoms that are reflected in structured data. As a result, the qualitative insights and nuanced observations captured in clinical notes become crucial for identifying early signs of sepsis.

Overall, the findings suggest that while structured data are sufficient for detecting more immediate signs of sepsis, unstructured clinical text becomes increasingly important for early prediction well before symptoms become apparent in structured data. This underscores the value of incorporating both types of data to enhance the accuracy of early sepsis detection.

Fig. 4 Comparing SERA algorithm performance with models without clinical text. We measure the change in performance for each diagnosis and prediction model when clinical text is added as additional predictors. Structured variables represent the models that only include vitals, investigations, and treatment data as predictors. Structured variables + text represent the models have additional clinical notes as predictors. a Compares the AUC of models with and without clinical notes. b Compares the sensitivity of models with and without clinical notes. c Compares the specificity of models with and without clinical notes.

Application of SERA algorithm in low sepsis prevalence environment

In a retrospective cohort study spanning 409 hospitals in the United States from 2009 to 2014, the prevalence of sepsis among hospitalized patients ranged from 1.8% to 12%, with a mean prevalence of 6% that remained relatively stable over time [19]. Despite this naturally low prevalence, many studies develop sepsis prediction algorithms using oversampled datasets where the prevalence is artificially inflated to as high as 50% [7,9,11,12,26,27,28,29,30,31]. Our study aims to address this gap by developing models for both oversampled scenarios, as seen in prior research, and for environments reflecting the actual low prevalence of sepsis in typical clinical settings.

As detailed in Table 3, models trained on datasets with a typical low prevalence of 6.15% can achieve high sensitivity, though with a naturally lower positive predictive value (PPV). To understand how varying prevalence levels affect the PPV of our algorithm, we simulated its performance under different prevalence rates, as shown in Table 4. For instance, in a 12-hour early prediction window, hospitals with a sepsis prevalence at the lower end of 1.8% will see an estimated PPV of 8.3% (95% CI: 0.89–8.73%). Conversely, if the prevalence reaches the higher end of 12%, the PPV improves significantly to 40.25% (95% CI: 38.94–41.58%).

These simulated results underscore the adaptability of the SERA algorithm across various clinical settings. The algorithm remains applicable and valuable in real-world environments where the prevalence of sepsis can vary significantly based on clinical specialty and institutional location.

Table 4 Simulated PPV at different sepsis prevalence levels.

PPV (95% CI)							
Algorithm	Prevalence	1.8%	6%	12%	20%	30%	50%
Diagnosis		0.11 (0.11-0.11)	0.30 (0.29-0.31)	0.48 (0.47-0.49)	0.63 (0.62-0.63)	0.74 (0.74-0.75)	0.87 (0.87-0.87)
4 h		0.11 (0.10-0.12)	0.30 (0.28-0.33)	0.48 (0.45-0.51)	0.63 (0.60-0.66)	0.75 (0.72-0.77)	0.87 (0.86-0.89)
6 h		0.09 (0.08-0.09)	0.25 (0.22-0.27)	0.41 (0.39-0.44)	0.56 (0.54-0.59)	0.69 (0.67-0.71)	0.84 (0.82-0.85)
12 h		0.08 (0.08-0.09)	0.24 (0.23-0.25)	0.40 (0.39-0.42)	0.55 (0.54-0.57)	0.68 (0.67-0.69)	0.83 (0.82-0.84)
24 h		0.07 (0.06-0.07)	0.20 (0.19-0.21)	0.35 (0.33-0.36)	0.49 (0.48-0.51)	0.63 (0.61-0.64)	0.80 (0.79-0.81)
48 h		0.06 (0.05-0.06)	0.17 (0.16-0.18)	0.30 (0.29-0.32)	0.44 (0.43-0.46)	0.58 (0.56-0.59)	0.77 (0.75-0.77)

1.8% (12%) represents the low (high) end of the typical sepsis prevalence observed in hospitals based on prior research [19]. Six percent represents the average sepsis prevalence of hospitals in the United States. Other prevalence percentages are for comparison purposes as they represent oversampled prevalence percentages typically observed in prior research.

III. DISCUSSION

The SERA algorithm offers a significant advancement in the early detection and management of sepsis, potentially transforming how clinicians identify and treat this critical condition. Effective early detection is crucial because sepsis can rapidly deteriorate, and timely intervention is essential to improve patient outcomes. Our study demonstrates that the SERA algorithm can identify 21–32% more patients at risk of sepsis compared to traditional methods used by hospital physicians, within the 4 to 48-hour window before sepsis onset. This additional lead time allows clinicians to begin treatment sooner, which is critical in reducing sepsis-related mortality.

However, it is important to address the issue of false positives inherent in any medical alert system. Excessive false positives can strain healthcare resources, as they necessitate additional diagnostic procedures and treatments. Moreover, frequent false alarms can erode physicians' trust in the alert system, leading to decreased responsiveness to future alerts and potentially diminishing the effectiveness of other best practice alerts integrated into electronic medical record (EMR) systems.

In contrast to these potential drawbacks, the SERA algorithm achieves a high true positive rate (TPR) while maintaining a relatively low false positive rate (FPR), outperforming traditional physician assessments. The algorithm's FPR is notably lower than that of hospital physicians' early sepsis detection efforts [33,34]. Additionally, simulations considering various sepsis prevalence levels indicate that the positive predictive value (PPV) of the SERA algorithm remains suitable for real-world clinical environments where sepsis prevalence is low. This balance between high TPR and low FPR enhances the algorithm's practical utility and reliability in clinical settings.

Overall, the SERA algorithm presents a robust tool for improving the early identification of sepsis, ultimately supporting better patient management and potentially reducing mortality associated with this severe condition. This study highlights the transformative potential of AI in enhancing clinical practice, particularly in the early detection and management of sepsis. By leveraging the SERA algorithm as a continuous, background monitoring system, healthcare providers can gain a crucial early warning tool for identifying patients at risk of sepsis. This proactive approach aims to address the common issue of overlooking sepsis cases, especially in high-pressure hospital environments where physicians are tasked with numerous responsibilities and rapid decision-making.

Key Implications and Applications:

- **AI as a Continuous Monitoring System:**
 - **Early Warning Capability:** The SERA algorithm can act as a "canary in a coal mine," continuously scanning patient data to flag potential sepsis cases before they become critical. This allows for timely intervention and could significantly enhance patient outcomes.
 - **Decision Support:** By providing an additional layer of oversight, the algorithm helps ensure that sepsis cases are not missed amidst the demands of busy clinical settings. It supports clinicians in making informed decisions, reducing the risk of sepsis-related complications.
- **Integration of Unstructured Data:**
 - **Unlocking Hidden Insights:** This study demonstrates the value of integrating unstructured data from clinical notes with structured EMR data. Given that unstructured data often contains rich, nuanced information, its systematic analysis through NLP can uncover insights not captured by structured data alone.
 - **Broader Applications:** The methodology used in this study can be applied beyond sepsis prediction. For other complex and critical clinical challenges, such as rare diseases or multifaceted symptoms, unstructured data analysis can provide valuable additional context and improve diagnostic accuracy.

- **Practical Implementation:**

- **System Setup:** The study details the practical setup of the SERA algorithm within existing EMR systems. This includes incorporating NLP techniques to process and analyze clinical notes alongside structured data, ensuring that the system is seamlessly integrated into routine clinical workflows.
- **Healthcare Efficiency:** The ability to analyze vast amounts of unstructured data systematically can enhance overall healthcare efficiency, reduce diagnostic delays, and improve patient management.

Future Directions:

- **Broader Clinical Applications:** Future research could explore the application of similar AI and NLP techniques to other critical medical conditions and patient monitoring systems.
- **Scalability and Adaptation:** Assessing how the SERA algorithm and its methodologies can be adapted to different hospital settings, specialties, and patient populations would be beneficial. This includes evaluating the algorithm's performance across diverse clinical environments and prevalence rates.
- **Enhanced Data Integration:** Further development could focus on integrating additional types of unstructured data, such as imaging and patient-generated health data, to provide a more comprehensive predictive tool.

In conclusion, this study reinforces the potential of AI and advanced data analytics to revolutionize clinical practice. By harnessing the full spectrum of EMR data—both structured and unstructured—the SERA algorithm exemplifies how innovative approaches can address complex clinical challenges and improve patient care outcomes.

Our study advances the application of Natural Language Processing (NLP) in healthcare research. While NLP has traditionally been employed in medical informatics to extract concepts, entities, events, and their associated attributes from free-text data—common in electronic medical records (EMRs)—we propose a new approach. Specifically, we suggest integrating NLP-processed text with traditional machine learning tools to enhance disease diagnosis and early detection.

Our findings indicate that clinicians' progress notes and other clinical documents (such as radiologist reports) stored in EMRs contain valuable patterns and themes. Extracting and analyzing these patterns can be particularly beneficial in clinical settings where symptoms may not be fully captured in structured EMR data. This analysis is crucial despite challenges such as medical abbreviations and the unique ways in which clinicians document diagnoses and treatment plans.

However, our study has limitations. Although we validated and tested our models with an independent sample from a subsequent time period, future research should involve external validation in diverse hospital settings to refine the SERA algorithm and strengthen our findings.

In conclusion, predictive algorithms like SERA, if designed to continuously access both structured and unstructured patient data, could enable round-the-clock monitoring of patients. This could significantly enhance early sepsis detection and intervention. While the SERA algorithm shows improved sensitivity and specificity compared to some physician diagnoses and prior machine learning methods, it is intended to complement rather than replace clinical expertise. We also advocate for the development of other NLP-enabled algorithms to support healthcare professionals and improve decision-making [35].

IV. METHOD

The raw datasets generated and analyzed during the current study will not be made publicly available due to privacy regulations under the HIPAA compliances. Approval was given to extract de-identified patient data from the EMR system for the purpose of building the predictive algorithm. Data extraction was performed using MySQL 8.0 from the Epic™ electronic medical record system.

Table 5 Topic categories.

Category	Count	Definition
Clinical status	28	Routine updates of clinical conditions as well as diagnosis (e.g., vitals) excluding lab and radio-diagnostic tests
Communication	3	Communication between staff
lab test	24	Orders and reports of lab or radio-diagnostic test results
Non-clinical status	2	Routine updates of non-clinical conditions
Social relationship	2	Information about family and social aspects of patient
Symptom	10	Clinical symptoms
Treatment	31	Treatment procedure or medication prescribed as well as the status of the treatment/ medication

The 100 topics are classified into seven different categories. The distribution of topics among categories is similar if 25, 50, 75, or 150 topics are extracted instead. Detailed results are available upon request from the corresponding authors.

The dataset comprises 5,317 patients admitted between April 2, 2015, and December 31, 2017, with a total of 114,602 clinical note entries. We divided this dataset into a training and validation sample and an independent hold-out test sample. The training and validation sample includes 3,722 patients and 80,162 clinical note entries, while the hold-out test sample contains 1,595 patients and 34,440 clinical note entries. A tenfold cross-validation methodology was employed to train and validate the model on the training and validation sample.

To assess the stability of the text topics identified by our text-mining algorithm, we specifically included patients admitted during a later period (May 10, 2017, to December 31, 2017) in the hold-out test sample. Each patient consultation instance (clinical note) was used as the unit of analysis (for more details, see Supplementary Fig. 2 in the Supplementary Information).

Data Sample

The raw datasets generated and analyzed during the current study will not be made publicly available due to privacy regulations under the HIPAA compliances. Approval was given to extract de-identified patient data from the EMR system for the purpose of building the predictive algorithm. Data extraction was performed using MySQL 8.0 from the Epic™ electronic medical record system.

The dataset comprises 5,317 patients admitted between April 2, 2015, and December 31, 2017, with a total of 114,602 clinical note entries. We divided this dataset into a training and validation sample and an independent hold-out test sample. The training and validation sample includes 3,722 patients and 80,162 clinical note entries, while the hold-out test sample contains 1,595 patients and 34,440 clinical note entries. A tenfold cross-validation methodology was employed to train and validate the model on the training and validation sample.

To assess the stability of the text topics identified by our text-mining algorithm, we specifically included patients admitted during a later period (May 10, 2017, to December 31, 2017) in the hold-out test sample. Each patient consultation instance (clinical note) was used as the unit of analysis (for more details, see Supplementary Fig. 2 in the Supplementary Information).

Text mining technique

In addition to the structured data presented in Table 1, our predictive model incorporates unstructured clinical notes, which are free-form text. To analyze this unstructured data, we first convert it into a numerical format using Latent Dirichlet Allocation (LDA). LDA, an unsupervised topic modeling technique, identifies topics based on patterns of word co-occurrence within the documents. This process generates topics from the clinical notes, represented as vectors where each topic's loading indicates the prominence of the topic in the text [36,37].

We followed a five-step process to handle the unstructured text data:

- **Anonymization:** In compliance with HIPAA guidelines, we removed all potential identifiers from the clinical notes. This included names, geographic locations, zip codes, ID numbers, dates, telephone/fax numbers, vehicle and device serial numbers, and email addresses.
- **Text Preprocessing:** We tokenized the text by eliminating punctuation, lemmatized words to their root forms, applied part-of-speech tagging, and removed stop words, including common articles and prepositions. Additionally, we excluded a specific list of medical-related stop words and phrases that, while frequent, do not contribute meaningful information to the topic modeling. A comprehensive list of these excluded terms is available upon request.
- **Term-Document Matrix Creation:** After preprocessing, we constructed a term-document matrix. In this matrix, rows represent the frequency of terms, and columns correspond to individual documents.

We applied a text filter to streamline the processed text by removing infrequent terms and adjusting the weights of terms with multiple occurrences. Fourth, we employed the Latent Dirichlet Allocation (LDA) algorithm to cluster the terms into various topics. According to existing literature, the optimal number of topics is somewhat subjective and depends on factors such as the number of observations and the anticipated diversity of topics within the dataset. To ensure robustness, we experimented with five different iterations of the LDA algorithm, generating 25, 50, 75, 100, and 150 topics. The analysis revealed that the results were qualitatively similar across all iterations. Consequently, for the sake of brevity, this paper reports on the 100-topic model.

It's important to note that developing the topics is a step required only during the model development and validation phase. When applying the text-mining algorithm to new clinical notes, the 100 pre-developed topics serve as a benchmark for evaluating the fit of the new notes to these topics. A high fit measure indicates strong similarity between the new clinical notes and the benchmark topics.

From a practical standpoint, we found that computing these fit values is not computationally demanding. For instance, estimating fit values for a test case with a lengthy clinical note of 1,806 words (compared to the median length of 840 words in our sample) takes only 0.17 seconds on an Intel i7 processor with 2.7 GHz and 16 GB of RAM, using SAS Enterprise Miner 14.2. Based on the

100-topic model, we presented the topics to three researchers who independently categorized them into seven overarching topic categories (see Table 5). All text-mining operations were conducted using SAS Enterprise Miner 14.2.

Machine learning algorithm

Ensemble methods are machine learning techniques that combine multiple classifiers to determine the final predicted outcome through a (weighted) voting process. These methods generally outperform individual classifiers due to their ability to leverage the strengths of each component model. Common ensemble methods include voting, bagging, stacking, and boosting [38,39].

In our primary analysis, we use a voting ensemble approach. Voting combines predictions from multiple base classifiers to arrive at a final prediction. In our case, we utilize two base classifiers: stochastic gradient descent (SGD) logistic regression and a random forest algorithm. The ensemble's final prediction is determined by averaging the probabilities predicted by these two models.

The first base classifier, SGD, is an optimization algorithm designed to minimize prediction errors by iteratively updating estimates based on previous iterations. It works by drawing random samples from the training data to estimate the model parameters, which are used to classify whether a patient has sepsis or not. The algorithm learns from each sampling iteration, refining parameter estimates to enhance classification accuracy until improvements become minimal.

For each iteration, the predicted parameter β is calculated, and the model is updated using the logistic regression equation:

$$\beta^{\text{new}} = \beta^{\text{old}} + \text{lr}(y - \hat{y})(1 - \hat{y})x \quad (1)$$

where β is the optimized parameter, α is the learning rate, error is the prediction error for the model in a particular iteration on the training data, $\hat{y}$ is the prediction made by the coefficients, and x is the input value. In our case, the input variables consist of a combination of structured variables (as indicated in Table 1) and the topic loadings from the 100 topics extracted during the text mining procedure.

The second classifier in our voting ensemble is a random forest classifier, with sepsis as the target variable. The final prediction probability is obtained by averaging the probabilities generated by both classifiers in our ensemble model.

Alternative estimators

For comparative analysis, we also evaluated two alternative estimators: Dagging and Gradient Boosting Trees (GBT).

Dagging is an ensemble method particularly effective with noisy data, which includes a significant amount of irrelevant information. In Dagging, we divide the training data into several disjoint, stratified samples. We then train a base classifier, specifically logistic regression with SGD as previously described, on each of these samples. The results from these trained models are then applied to the validation data. The final prediction is obtained by averaging the predictions across all sub-samples and using a voting mechanism.

Gradient Boosting Trees (GBT) constructs powerful prediction models by aggregating multiple decision trees. The core concept involves sequentially building a series of trees, where each new tree aims to correct the errors made by the preceding ones. GBT comprises three main components: a loss function to be optimized, a weak learner (decision trees) for making predictions, and an additive model that incrementally adds weak learners to minimize the loss function. The training process involves adding a fixed number of trees or stopping when the loss function reaches an acceptable level or no longer improves on the validation dataset. All ensemble machine learning procedures were performed using KNIME Analytics Platform (version 4.1.6).

Other Model Diagnostics

To evaluate the trade-offs between positive predictive value (PPV, also known as precision) and sensitivity (recall), refer to the precision-recall curves shown in Supplementary Fig. 3 of the Supplementary Information. Additionally, calibration curves for the SERA algorithm can be found in Supplementary Fig. 4 of the Supplementary Information.

Fig. 5 Workflow for the setup of SERA algorithm within the clinical environment.

- A proposed workflow for the SERA algorithm to operate in the background and provide alerts when key events (such as ward shift handovers) are triggered.
- A proposed workflow for the SERA algorithm to run immediately after a physician updates a patient's clinical notes in the EMR system.

V. PROPOSED SETUP OF THE SERA ALGORITHM IN A CLINICAL ENVIRONMENT

We propose two operational modes for implementing the SERA algorithm in a clinical setting:

Background Mode

In this mode, the SERA algorithm operates in the background, running during key clinical events when the latest patient data is available, such as during ward shift handovers. If the risk score generated by the algorithm exceeds a predetermined cut-off, the Electronic Medical Records (EMR) system will alert the physician. Alternatively, if additional computing resources are available, hospitals may opt to run the algorithm at fixed hourly intervals. For a large hospital with 500 beds, scoring all patients individually takes approximately 90 seconds. This setup ensures continuous, time-based sepsis risk assessment for all patients within the hospital. (Refer to Fig. 5a for the workflow of this mode.)

Ad-Hoc Mode

In this mode, the SERA algorithm operates on an ad-hoc basis. It is triggered immediately after a physician updates clinical note in the EMR system. The algorithm calculates the sepsis risk score only following these updates, providing a decision support tool to flag potential sepsis cases. According to the study, the SERA algorithm demonstrates superior performance compared to physicians in the early detection of sepsis, making it a valuable early warning indicator to assist physicians in diagnosing and managing patient care. (Refer to Fig. 5b for the workflow of this mode.)

Data Availability

The raw datasets generated and analyzed during the current study will not be made publicly available due to privacy regulations under the HIPAA compliances. These datasets include sensitive clinical information and textual notes written by physicians, which could potentially compromise patient privacy or consent. However, the processed textual data, which includes patient vitals, is available upon reasonable request from the corresponding author for review purposes.

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